

Reference Board: Method with Focus on Emotion for the Conception of New Products in Design

Viviane Gaspar Ribas, Departamento de Desenho Industrial, Universidade Federal do Paraná, UFPR – Brazil

André Luiz Battaiola, Departamento de Desenho Industrial / Universidade Federal do Paraná, UFPR – Brazil

Bruna Cozer Montenegro, Departamento de Desenho Industrial / Universidade Federal do Paraná, UFPR – Brazil

Joana Fernandes de Andrade, Departamento de Desenho Industrial / Universidade Federal do Paraná, UFPR – Brazil

Yuri Cristian Vieira Queiroz, Departamento de Desenho Industrial / Universidade Federal do Paraná, UFPR – Brazil

Abstract

Technological development has allowed industries to increase product quality dramatically, some segments offer products with small differences in terms of quality, functionality and price. Emotional aspects can create a product differential. In order to accomplish that, a product should stimulate users' sensibility and interest. Theoretical knowledge is the first requirement for a designer to incorporate emotional aspects into a product design. The second requirement is his/her sensibility, an emotional view of the world, which can be obtained by experiencing different kinds of emotional stimulus, such as colors, smell, music, etc. The third requirement is a perfect combination between rationality, particular to project's technical aspects, and project's emotional issues. This paper describes a method to reach this combination based on the main results of a multiple case study focused on the process of color selection.

Keywords: Tools and Methods; Reference Board; Synesthesia; Color.

Introduction

The intention of this article is to approach the development of a method, named Reference Board, in which the macro element COLOR is used as a standard pattern in order to show that emotion stimulated through the acquisition of knowledge - resulting from the many human expressions - may be the new ingredient of the creative process in the conception of new products.

To a designer who yearns for the success of his products, its essential to incorporate values into his work stimulating emotion on the users and consequently pursuing objects that are friendly, because the market is growing more competitive and the products are technically

equivalent. The originality contained in an object will be its emotional appeal, which makes the consumer fall in love.

In this article, three projects with focus on the macro element color will be exemplified through the utilization of music, nature photographs and chromatic illumination, which can be used as means of creating new ideas so that the designer will be able to establish the Reference Board mentioned before.

The theoretical concept as a base for the designer to incorporate emotion to the project

The designer is a professional who intends to solve problems originated from the interfaces between man and his surroundings. He must develop all kinds of abilities and competencies to its maximum, acquiring knowledge from all areas, so that when he faces these problems, he will be able to distinguish the whole and its parts.

He should also be willing to develop the capacity of “knowing how to see”, observing the information emitted by all kinds of human expression with precision, in order to transfer these acquired experiences to his new conceived objects.

In the post-industrial revolution period, the process of conception of new products was the methodology of projects of Engineering in which the main aspect was functionality.

Since the 80's, however, with the improvement of the communication process, consumers became more demanding and the industry more competitive, so that functionality, by itself, does not answer the demands of the market. Therefore, the current design methodologies of the process of Design have searched for new methods that allow the creation of innovating ideas. Nowadays, creativity is considered the heart of Design, consisting of the process of products' development in its design stages as a main ingredient, hence, it should be stimulated.

Allied to creativity, the component emotion must be better understood, explored and applied in Design. So, even if the utilization of Design Methods in Engineering provide satisfactory results to the designer, they are absolutely insufficient nowadays, because the consumer seeks, more and more, products that are *“able to play the strings of the heart, stroke it's*

emotions, captivate culture and reason, (...) able yet, to awaken it's active participation and at the same time, touch it" – Claudio Salocchi.

This causes the designer not only to develop his abilities, competencies and creativity, but also, above all, to mold them in the vision of the Italian designer Alessandro Mendini, to whom *"the object is a friend of men, a smiling and affectionate company"*. Moreover, in order for a professional of design to achieve out standing projects, it is indispensable that he should be able to aggregate more value to his objects, not only the esthetic, technical, functional and cultural ones, but, mainly, the emotional ones. Thus, through the use of elements, like: COLOR, shape, texture, smells, flavors, sounds and movements, the object will be able to transmit to the consumer a vast amount of information.

To assure that to the consumer notices the implicit and explicit qualities of an object and to use this more easily and efficiently, it is necessary that he feels attracted and infatuated by it. Therefore, aggregating values to objects means to stimulate all areas that comprehend the human emotion: vision, hearing, tact, taste and smell; thus the more sensations stimulated and awakened, more efficient the objects will be.

Donald A Norman (2004: 19), in his book *Emotion Design*, teaches *"why beautiful objects really work better"*. He gives us, among several examples, a teapot (see Figure 1) that has a whistle in its beak, which makes harmonious tune in the passage of steam. The consumer receives information that warns him that the tea is ready, and has his heart touched by a sweet melody.

Figure 1, Photographs of the teapots exemplified by Donald A Norman
Source: Norman, 2004.

In this example Norman's target is to demonstrate that the designer will be able to obtain better results through the stimulus of several senses, as well as supplying needs by functionality. He will be also satisfying desires and human aspirations, due to the fact of working the human senses through the arts, perceived by many as the maximum human expression.

A better understanding of the functioning of the human mind, as well as the brain information's processing [1] is needed in order to obtain results never reached before. The designer should gather enough knowledge to stimulate the human senses and, consequently, human emotion, not only his, as well as the consumer's.

Profiting from synesthesia [2], phenomenon that occurs when a person is able to mix the senses – vision, hearing, tact, taste and smell; being able, for example, to taste an image or to color a song (see Figure 2) – incorporates it into the creative process of Design. The information given by objects will be more rapidly noticed due to the fact that more than one sense is being enhanced. As the consumer faces an object molded with feelings, he will understand the characteristics of this object, since his stimulated senses will awaken his soul and touch his heart. Unavoidably, the user will be amazed and will wish to possess this object.

Figure 2, Image demonstrating the brain in Synesthesia
Source: Ramachandran & Hubbard (2003: 50).

The Method REFERENCE BOARD

For the creation of a Reference Board, the designer has to acquire a repertoire of knowledge (information/symbols) (see Figure 3), in order to understand the real interests that conduct a man's life. It is the designer's primordial task to experience everything that surrounds him: sounds, lights, shapes, colors and flavors. Later on, the mind will be stimulated by a brainstorm, coming from the several human expressions, teaching him "how to see". This will provide information to create the Reference Board.

Figure 3, Reference Board to stimulate Emotion in a design environment.
Source: elaborated by the authors of this article, Design Emotion 2004.

This article intends to demonstrate that the designer, surrounded by real experiences, through the multiple human expressions, implicating from the processing of mind information, associates the acquired knowledge by the experiences mentioned before, leading to insights, dejavus, which allows innovation to be incorporated in new objects.

The loaned methodologies of Engineering will serve as tools that will speed up creation process, but it will be the heart beating for passion coming from these experiences, the new ingredient that will lead to new solutions translated in friendly objects.

As a creator, the designer is influenced by similar situations to those lived by the users of its objects. Which human being, when hearing the chord of a piano, or the sound of sea waves, or, smelling a sweet perfume, or feeling solar rays, or even tasting a yummy strawberry pie covered with whip cream, has not created imaginary sets or mentally projected a new way of life?

Three examples of chromatic solutions in projects will be presented in order to demonstrate that it is possible to create a REFERENCE BOARD.

It is given credit that, due to being in touch with objects that shows chromatically well solved solutions, people will be enchanted over the beauty of these objects, making these objects part of the consumers life, its smiling and affectionate company.

COLOR, macro-element of the objects' configuration, was used to illustrate that this macro-element is being treated in a vast and simultaneous way, during the conception of new objects. Finally obtaining better results that awaken the human emotion.

Examples of projects with focus on COLOR

Example 1

The first example shows that the use of Music (voice of the soul, heart's lullaby) can unchain a mental process of input, processing and output of information, that sends the designer to a contemplation environment and inspiration, assisting the creation process. This, by the way, is not considered as news. According to Filipe Salles (2002: 89), "*the first scientifically researched relation between sound and image was the chromatic instance*", he continues describing that this relation is "*an old knowledge that associated these vibratory instances in priesthood rituals in diverse religions, always accompanied by determined apparel of specific colors, besides mantras and incense*".

Other authors, such as: Priest Kircher (1602-1680), Priest Mersenn (1588-1648), Jameson (1844), Rimington (1893), Von Helmholtz (1910), Tomas Young (1954) and, finally, Scriabin (1911), according to what Israel Pedrosa (2002: 57) taught us also looked for parameters for relations between musical and chromatic harmony. However, it was Johann Wolfgang Von Goethe, in his Treaty named *Doctrine of the Colors* - that, with the objective of unmasking the Chromatic phenomena in an aesthetic intention, that elapses from them, besides his erudition and deep knowledge of the poet of physical sciences, in special, Newtonian - he made something really significant, more than one chromatic Treaty.

Another great master, Russian painter Wassily Kandinski, defined that in painting, there are two constructions: the simple ones, that are melodic; and the complex ones that are symphonic. For Kandinski apud Irma Beckett (1994: 355) Color "*is the basic tone, the eyes are the harmony and the soul is the piano with many strings. The artist is the hand that plays, playing one or other key to provoke vibrations in the soul.*" In his Treaty *Point and Line on*

Plan (1997), Kandinski uses the analogy with music to describe graphical characteristics, point, line and plan provide varied gamma of graphical comparisons to the sonorous ones.

The intention of this article is to show the designer a way in the construction of chromatic solutions that can be placed, according to Israel Pedrosa (2002: 62) at the service of the highest aesthetic purposes (another attribute of design).

Figure 4 is the result obtained by the information (sensations) caught by musical notes, processed by the brain, generating a state of anxiety and excitement in the author, that allows him to express and to register the interpretations of these musical notes in chromatic and formal representations, and as a consequence, the creation of this painting, chromatically harmonious, formally organized and beautiful.

Figure 4, Painting obtained by musical stimuli.
Source: Maggi, Rodrigo, academic of Design at UFPR, Brazil, 2003.

The song *You could be mine* of Guns’N Roses, chosen by Maggi has strong drumbeats, that is the reason for the use of hot and dark colors and circular and linear drawings in repetition.

The singer’s high sounding voice, leads to the use of cold colors, and linear and undulatory drawings. Other musical elements were also represented, but the most important thing in this example is to know the dissociation of reason and emotion in the human mind. The designer

uses music to stimulate the brain and creation, catching information that touches his heart, his soul. Reason acts in order to organize, spatially, the sensations perceived by emotion.

It means both the mental lobes and the information processing are activated. The computational theory of the mind explains that emotion, stimulated by music, unchains mental processes that allow the designer to create his REFERENCE BOARD, and makes the mental processing of information more pleasant and harmonious. With this, the generation of new ideas will be facilitated through the association of information of this human expression, music, to the existing others already in his memory.

Now, reader, picture yourself creating a decorative fabric print, listening to Mozart. Did you imagine the colors, shapes, and the innovating solutions that your mind could create?

Example 2

In the second example, (see Figure 5) the use of an image bank of nature photographs is shown. The designer as another resource to create the Reference Board must systematically explore them.

Figure 5, Harmonic Chromatic project obtained by nature photographs stimulation
Source: elaborated by the authors of this article, Design Emotion 2004.

In this example, the use of a image bank of nature photographs allowed the designer - impregnated by visual information and enraptured by the beautiful images of the nature, during the conception of new products, with focus in chromatic project - to associate the information established in the project briefing to the concepts of the colors that he intended to

apply in the object. With this, the professional frees himself of having, necessarily, to use the rules, the chromatic standards, already established in purely technical manuals.

The Figure 5 presents the result of a task, where its project briefing established the concepts of the developed product, which defined a group of word-stimulation full of meaning.

The designer filled with knowledge - color meanings, physiological and psychological influences in man, use of colors in human history, cultural aspects of colors, its mystical meanings, and mainly, the sensations caused by the colors - using his image bank, in this case nature photographs, to associate the concepts of the product, to the ones of colors and in this association finding the chromatic solutions that better represent these analogous information, concept of the product and concept of the colors.

The process continues when the designer captures one palette of colors existing in these photographs and, from it, he develops several chromatic combinations, applying them in the drawings generated for the product, analyzing them individually and, later, selecting them, having in target the concepts of the object. This will make it possible, in a conscientious and directed act of creation process, to establish which of the best chromatic alternatives will be used in the object bought by the users.

Therefore, it is the designer's task to learn how to notice information presented by nature that, incontrovertibly beautiful, can perfectly be applied in his graphical projects.

Now, readers imagine that there is a gigantic screen in your design office and nature photographs are projected in the screen; this makes you relax and present you fantastic chromatic solutions. Have you already imagined the possibilities that your brain would process when developing, for example, a project of perfume packing?

Example 3

In the third example it is demonstrated that COLOR can be used to create a competitive distinguishing in means of transportation, such as: automobile, bus, aircraft, *etc.* The manufacturers of these means of transportation recognize that it is necessary to invest in human necessities and center efforts in the technology and creation of electronic devices such as: board computers and airbags. But it is also necessary to invest in solutions that awaken

and take care of the consumers' desires, attracting him and making him loyal. It is necessary to motivate the consumer to a buying mode. In this context, the designer must create solutions that make the consumer leave reality and live in an imaginary world.

The designer uses COLORS in his environment projects and it is essential that he tries the sensations provoked by them. One of the mechanisms that the academic and the professional can use to understand the influences of colors is the generation of situations that allows them to enter in direct contact with colors, delighting themselves at the touch in their skin and their soul (see Figure 6).

Figure 6, Photographs of Chromatic Spaces for Color Perception.
Source: Developed by the academics of UFPR, 2003.

The colors modify the metabolic, physiological and psychological states that generate sensations of heat or cold, fear or peace, sadness or joy. The designer living these corporal sensations notices this information more easily, making him understand and use them in a more efficient and creative way. In the case of an environment project, the designer can, for example, create innovative solutions in lighting systems, that propitiates the user to enter in an imaginary world, where his emotions are awakened by the sensations influenced by the colors.

Phobias generated by the tension state that some environments (airplanes, bus, elevators, *etc*) cause can be diminished by the correct use of colors. This way, the user feels more

comfortable and safe, and, consequently, happier, which might be decisive in achieving fidelity in a consumer.

The environment shown in Figure 7, the interior of an airplane, illustrates the modification that can be obtained through the application of colors in the lighting system.

Figure 7, Chromatic Illumination in the airplane's interior.
Source: <http://www.upperclasssuite.com>. Checking Date: 17/03/2004.

Conclusion

This article intended to demonstrate that emotion - as long, as the designer during his academic and professional formation understands it in its importance - may be a new and essential ingredient in the development of projects. When coming across challenges presented in a briefing, the professional will dominate knowledge that will facilitate innovating ideas. And this, not only in technical, aesthetic, functional terms, but also, over all, emotional knowledge.

In this perspective, it is of utmost importance to awake in the customers the desire for objects through feelings incorporated in them. It is also necessary that every creative being, in this case the designer, must have in mind that technology must be developed by man and for man, in an attempt of making humanity understand that the real meaning of life is to love and to be loved.

It was demonstrated that it is possible to create a repertoire of knowledge through the utilization of a new method called REFERENCE BOARD. Using COLOR and other elements of the objects' configuration it is possible to obtain better results thus creating objects with competitive differentials.

It was also demonstrated that COLOR, due to being such a special element, so infatuating and endowed with many unique characteristics, deserves to be respected, to be studied with scientific severity, never being left for the end, as just a decorative element!

It was shown that COLOR, in the development of new products, can assist the designer to point out the qualities of an object. It has to be thought, studied and respected as a macro element. The differential in a product, even if it is technically equivalent to its competitor, lies in the professionalism in which the team of designers deals with all the details of a project, like the pianist who gives himself to music.

To the designer who intends to succeed, it is essential to learn to look around himself, listening better to colors, feeling shapes, tasting sounds, so, trying the many aspects of the world. He must, mainly, "wake up" for the discovery and the formulation of solutions to the presented problems.

The designer must also understand all the ways of life and human expression, either musical, literary, poetical, sensitive or chromatic. Moreover, he must be holistic, eclectic, particular and unique.

Experiencing your own search is, also, of vital importance in a conscientious act and conducted in an attempt to organize colors, shapes, lines, sounds, movements, materials and flavors, with the intention of transmitting human ideas, feelings concerning the world, desires and more than that, trying to help others to solve the problems that show up from human and environmental diversity.

And, finally, being a designer is a life practice, a privileged way of articulating intelligence, leading the thought, guiding the formation of men culture, of what is real, of what is sensible, of what is impossible to imagine, because through his methods of problem solution, they distinguish divergent and convergent, logical and structuralized thoughts, mobilizing and

putting into motion structures in search of what is new, in order to produce operationally and industrially the construction of a more inhabitable and honorable place for humanity.

NOTES

[1] The Science that deals with the knowledge of human mind is the cognitive that nowadays has appropriated of the computational theory of the mind. According to Pinker (1999: 36), “the computational theory of the mind is the processing of information, or computation, that reside, data patterns in logical relations which are independent of the physical mean that conducts them.

[2] For Ramachandran & Hubbard (2003: 50) “synesthesia, of the Greek root “syn”, means “together”, and “aisthesis”, “perception”. Disturb that affects people, of normal aspects, in which the brain processes sensorial information and uses it to make abstract connections among apparently non-related inputs”, in other words, you may think of cold when you see an ice cube, but you certainly won’t feel cold.

REFERENCES

Baxter, M. et. al. 1999. *Product Design: A Practical Guide to Systematic Methods of New Product Development*. Stanley Thornes Pub Ltd; Reissue edition ISBN: 0748741976.

Beckett, I.W. et al.. 2000. *Wendy's Story of Painting*. LOCAL DA PUBLICACAO: DK Publishing; 2nd edition.

Goethe, Johann Wolfgang Von. 1993. *Doutrina das cores*. São Paulo: Nova Alexandria, ISBN 8586075620.

Kandinsky, Wassily. 2001. Ponto e linha sobre plano. São Paulo: Martins Fontes, ISBN 8533605781.

Mendini, Alessandro. 2004. [Online] Available from URL: < <http://www.the-artists.org/ArtistView.cfm?id=8A01F9C6-BBCF-11D4-A93500D0B7069B40>>. [Accessed 2004 May 26th].

Norman, Donald A.. 2004. *Boas razões para as máquinas sentirem medo*. Brasil, São Paulo: Scientific American, ano 02, nº21, pág.18-19.

Pedrosa, I.. 2002. *Da Cor À Cor Inexistente*. São Paulo: Editora Leo Christiano.

Pinker, Steven. 1999. *How the Mind Works*. Publisher: W.W. Norton & Company. ISBN: 0393318486.

Ramachandran, Vilayanur S. e Hubbard, Edward M..2003. *Ouvindo as cores e degustando as formas*. Brasil, São Paulo: Scientific American, ano 02, nº13, pág. 49-55.

Salles, Filipe. 2002. *Imagens Musicais ou Música Visual - Um estudo sobre as afinidades entre o som e a Imagem, baseado no Filme "Fantasia (1940) de Walt Disney"*. Dissertação de Mestrado, Programa de Pós-Graduação em Comunicação e Semiótica da PUC/SP, Defendida Brasil, São Paulo. Orientador: José Luiz Martinez.

Salocchi, Claudio. *Gemma Gioielli*. 2004. [Online] Available from URL: <<http://www.gemmagioielli.com/inglese/index.htm>>. [Accessed 2004 May 26th].

Prof. Dr. André Luiz Battaiola is a professor of Design in the Universidade Federal do Paraná/ Brazil. He is vice Head of the Department of Design in the Universidade Federal do Paraná. Actually he teaches Image Analyses. He also is doctor in Supercomputeres and Scientific Visualizacion in the Universidade de São Paulo.

Prof. Ms.C. Viviane Gaspar Ribas is a professor of Design in the Universidade Federal do Paraná/ Brazil. Nowadays she teaches Theoric and Practic of Color and Ergonomics. She has a mastership in Production Enginiere in the Universidade Federal de Santa Catarina.

Bruna Cozer Montenegro is a student of Graphic Design in the Universidade Federal do Paraná/ Brazil. Nowadays she makes part of research group in the University.

Joana Fernandes de Andrade is a student of Graphic Design in the Universidade Federal do Paraná/ Brazil. Nowadays she makes part of research group in the University.

Yuri Cristian Vieira Queiros is a student of Graphic Design in the Universidade Federal do Paraná/ Brazil. Nowadays he makes part of research group in the University.